

Recommended citation: Pourtoulidou, D., & Frey, A. (2021). Blended Learning in Aerospace Companies ■ Training Course: Conversion of a Classroom-based Training to Blended Format. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1171-1179). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650407.

BLENDED LEARNING IN AEROSPACE COMPANIES' TRAINING COURSE: CONVERSION OF A CLASSROOM-BASED TRAINING TO BLENDED FORMAT

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Conference Key Areas: *Methods, formats and essential elements for online/blended learning, HE & Business*

Keywords: *entry-level employee training, individualization, digitalization, aerospace software development*

ABSTRACT

A network of German aerospace companies and academic institutions initiated the research and the development of a (re)training for new employees who enter aerospace software development with different educational and professional backgrounds. Based on the analysis of the companies' and the labour market's demands, a classroom-based training was designed. After implementing and evaluating the training, the participants' feedback led towards further development beyond traditional classroom boundaries and the individualization of the training material.

To fulfil the participants' needs, the blended approach was chosen among other learning approaches. A blended format was developed to surpass the limitations of classroom-based training and includes various teaching methods and customized content while still offering face-to-face interaction. This paper describes the conversion from the classroom-based training to a blended format for new employees entering aerospace companies.

This conversion required selecting the suitable teaching methods and the topics that ought to be converted and conveyed digitally. The content, the difficulty level and the pros and cons of each teaching method were taken as criteria to determine the selection. Depending on their educational and professional background, the participants can choose the content and their learning environment without time and place restrictions.

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The training is currently under development and scheduled to be conducted in autumn 2021. The evaluation following the training will offer feedback from the participants' perspectives to endorse the focus on their learning needs. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation, alternatives such as online training are considered but the blended format remains its priority.

1 INTRODUCTION

Back in 2017, before the challenges that COVID-19 brought to education worldwide, a network of eight German companies formed under the publicly funded research project "Avionic System Software Embedded Technologie-2" (ASSET-2) formulated the demand for a training course for new employees entering the aerospace industry. Ingolstadt University of Applied Sciences (Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt – THI) designed a classroom-based training to cover the companies' demands for a common elementary introduction to aerospace software development. These demands derive from the recruitment process in the aerospace industry that also affects employees from pertinent fields, e.g. automotive engineering and STEM. Aerospace companies have to reach out to software engineers and architects with a wide variety of academic and professional backgrounds. Afterwards, the challenge remains at each company to train the new software engineers through further training courses or whilst on the job.

The development of the classroom-based training, as the fundamental training development strategies indicate, started with the needs analysis; followed by the implementation and the evaluation of the training. The feedback from the participants and the companies revealed the need for individualization of the training. The participants expressed their individual learning needs and were in favour of the opportunity to self-regulate which parts of the training they will attend. Based on this feedback, the further development of the training started in 2020 under the publicly funded research project "Integrierte Design- und Entwicklungsumgebung für Aerospace" (IDEA) aiming at a customized outcome for the participants within a network of twelve German aerospace companies and academic institutions. It sought to cover the learning needs of the individual employee and the different companies' demands by supporting his/her prior experience. The companies' demands concern also the necessity for data protection and confidentiality regarding the employees and the training material.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Catalano concludes that Blended Learning (BL) enables the personalization of the learning process by using different learning and teaching methods physically and virtually [1]. BL involves the use of technology and remote learning and combines classroom and eLearning sessions [2]. This learning approach enables the transition to the current demanding situations with numerous benefits. The potential of personalization and individualization of the training is extremely important for this training for the introduction of new employees in the aerospace industry. The classroom-based training from the ASSET-2 project has a duration of eight days,

which can take place in either two or four parts. Both possibilities demand extra time for travelling to the training facility. The effort to find common available dates for employees from different companies and cities while also having a sufficient number of participants at training is challenging and delays the implementation of the training. A delay for an employee can undermine the value of attending. For example, if an employee waits six months to take part in the classroom-based training, he/she may already have needed the knowledge that the course contains. Afterwards, when the training finally takes place, he/she may have already acquired the knowledge that the training intends to transmit.

Considering such problems, this blended learning format aims to enable employees to access the content and obtain useful knowledge for their new position before the face-to-face (f2f) sessions. This research implements the “flipped model” of blended learning [3], [4]. After the online part, the participants attend the f2f sessions and meet with the trainer where they have the opportunity to acquire competences through different practical exercises. Thus, a blended format for this training lowers the cost and establishes exchange opportunities for the network among the companies and their employees.

3 METHODOLOGY OF CONVERSION

The starting point of this research is the evaluation of the ASSET-2 classroom-based training that took place in 2019. The ASSET-2 classroom-based training is divided into five modules and lasts 56 hours. Questionnaires and interviews were conducted with 11 participants of the training, 16 subject matter experts and eight managers of this field. The evaluation of the classroom-based training revealed the need for individualization and customization of the training. The outcome in 2019 when companies and employees were hesitant towards online trainings was the preference for f2f sessions. The benefits of expert discussion sessions were considered a highlight for such entry-level employee training. The research of IDEA project aims at the customization of the classroom-based training for employees entering the aerospace industry. Customization provides learners with the opportunity to choose and construct mostly independently the training they need. How a classroom-based training can offer this independence and individualization is answered through digital technologies. During the last year many, if not all, universities, schools, and educators were unexpectedly forced to move classroom-based courses into an online environment. Courses about various topics, from numerous fields and for different audiences were obligated to switch to online. In many cases what happened was the substitution by digitalizing the material that was already available and delivering it via a learning management system (LMS) that acts as an online platform. From lecturing live in a classroom, the trainer began lecturing through a camera live or asynchronously. The obligatory transition to a remote working and learning lifestyle is not necessarily equal to a transformation of the training courses. Different terms try to describe such processes but neither all mean the same nor reflect the desirable and ideal process. The term “conversion” has been chosen for this research because it describes the act and active decisions about the process [5]. This differentiates it from “transition” that refers only to the process of changing from one state to another.

The goal of this blended format is the customization of the training in order to serve the personal learning needs of the new employees. This format includes an online part and a f2f session. The online part takes place first. The participants have a period of two months to access asynchronously the content via the LMS. The LMS contains all digital materials such as e.g. videos, documents, a discussion forum and chat sessions. The obligation to complete the online course materials before the f2f session depends on and is determined by the participants. They can access the training material any time from a place of their choice. The obligation to complete it does not necessarily apply to all material because the participants can differentiate the content depending on their educational and professional background, needs and preferences. They are able to choose which part they will devote more time to and if they skip or re-watch a video. The introduction and the structure of the training along with the information for each chapter and subchapter provide a brief overview of the subjects. The participants are informed about the content of the video and if they are already familiar with it, they can fast forward a sequence or skip it. The material is always available which means that they can return at a later time and watch it, in case a question appears.

For the conversion of the classroom-based training to a blended format, the curriculum design of the classroom-based training is necessary to be subjected to change. The demands about the content of the training remain the same, but the teaching and learning methods ought to change according to the blended format. Since the learning and teaching methods change, the curriculum design of the classroom-based training had to be converted because it cannot serve the blended format. The curriculum design incorporates the learning objectives, teaching and learning methods, time schedule, structure and assessment.

The way a training developer should choose the suitable method and tool for every chapter is answered through the following criteria: The differentiation starts by choosing which content will take place online and which f2f. The blended format, as explained above, ought to have a f2f session for practical exercises, expert discussion and direct live exchange opportunities among participants and between participants and trainers or experts.

1. The first criterion is the distinction according to the chosen teaching method of each subchapter. Possible teaching methods for this training are practical exercises, group projects, discussion sessions, expert discussions and instructor-led training (ILT). According to the theories behind these teaching methods, some are more suitable for f2f sessions, while others for the online part of the training. The learning objectives affect the method of delivery according to which skills needed to be developed. There are practical exercises where the participants ought to work hands-on or need access to laboratories or specific software. Therefore, practical exercises and group projects are a priority for the f2f sessions, where the application can take place and the participants have direct contact with their fellow participants and trainers. Discussion sessions among participants can take place in f2f and online using various tools without any drawbacks. The categorisation for these sessions will be finalised after taking into consideration the following two criteria. Expert discussions suit both options. However, since direct contact

between participants and experts is desired, expert discussions are also implemented into the f2f sessions. Otherwise, it would be possible to organize such an online session for discussion among experts and participants. ILT can serve well the learning objectives in an online eLearning environment [6], [7]. Therefore, ILT is classified to be part of online sessions and practical exercises, group projects and expert sessions of the f2f sessions.

2. The second criterion is the subject of each chapter and each subchapter. The difficulty level, the depth and the complexity of each subject influence also the decision between online or f2f sessions. The comprehension of these subjects requires examples and practical application. Theoretical parts related to the content of the exercises need to be summarized and performed in the f2f session as an introduction to the practical exercises. Regarding examples that can be included in every teaching method, eLearning can enhance considerably their presentation with e.g. animations, but there are still cases where the trainer can predict that additional explanations will be requested [7], [8].
3. The third criterion is the overall structure and planning of the training. The available time for f2f sessions can affect the final categorisation. Here, subchapters such as discussion sessions that can take place online as well as in f2f session, will be respectively divided depending on the available time and the thematic relation with the rest of the f2f subjects. Subchapters e.g. that can offer a thematic summary before an exercise can also belong to the f2f sessions.

With categorizing the subjects using these criteria, the training is divided into two kinds of sessions: online and f2f. The training developer examines in detail which online platform and tool can serve the online part, always taking into consideration the learning objectives of each chapter. The training budget and the restrictions of participants' companies need to be examined here thoroughly to avoid complications afterwards when conducting the training. This blended format allows the learner to individualise and self-regulate the online part. This concerns apart from the content, also, the teaching and learning methods of the online part. The research aims at the individualisation by examining the different types of training videos and the preference on the teaching methods by the participants in order to enhance the comprehension of the subjects. Such are videos where the trainer is a) facing the camera, b) recording with voice-over or c) broadcasting live a video. In a) there may be a green screen behind the trainer in order to change the background and/or add slides with relevant information e.g. written text, animations or graphics. For b) the options are similar as the participants see the slides, animations, graphics etc. while only hearing the trainer's voice. These two options can be recorded either with one camera (front or rear-facing), with multiples cameras or via software screen recording. A Webinar is option c); a live video broadcast in which the learners participate synchronously and the camera can be recording from different perspectives as mentioned above. Other tools used on online platforms are discussion forums, chat rooms and quizzes. To list here the vast variety of tools available for an eLearning training developer is impossible; for the sake of brevity, we referred to the relevant tools for this training.

At this point, the learning methods have been chosen, but not the duration of the online and f2f sessions. The online sessions need to have a small duration between five and 15 minutes. The f2f sessions will be planned at the THI with the intention to exchange views within the practical exercises and converse about different roles. We incorporate additional social activities outside of usual working hours to enhance the networking among the participants of the network that hold different positions. Hence, the participants gain insights on other companies' approaches and procedures. The online aspect of blended training brings out further features that need thorough consideration and planning such as the development of videos for the online part. The user experience of the participants in eLearning affects the learner's experience [8], [9]. Therefore, the design of the platform, the duration of a session, the features, the video and audio quality, the quality of the background, slides or figures and everything that is shown in a video and every tool used on the platform needs to be previously examined and tested.

This blended format ends with the evaluation. The participants complete the training with an online exam for the assessment of the learning. They decide for themselves when and if they take the exam depending on their personal goals and company's demands. In addition, the participants will be asked in form of questionnaires and interviews to assess the content, the learning methods and the structure of the training. The evaluation aims to elicit the learning preferences of the employees after participating in this training and their capability of applying the acquired knowledge. This aims at the further development and potential improvement of the blended format. The questionnaires and interviews will also enlighten the second perspective of the evaluation; how the research goal is achieved. The participants evaluate if their learning needs are covered with this format. The investigation of their opinions and satisfaction level regarding their experience with the training's customization are the desired outcome.

The evaluation occurs in three steps; firstly, the participants will answer the online questionnaire (Q1) before starting the training, secondly, the questionnaire after participating in the training (Q2) and thirdly, three months after the training they will assess the training in a semi-structured interview (Fig. 1). The first online questionnaire (Q1) prior to the training investigates the learning needs of the participants at the beginning of their onboarding. In Q2, the participants assess the training and in which level the materials of the online and f2f sessions and the learning and teaching methods correspond to their needs and learning preferences. The interview takes place purposely three months after the training so that the participants are able to evaluate the training after gaining relevant experience in their new position.

Fig. 1. Timeline

4 IMPLEMENTATION

Currently, the training is divided into online and f2f sessions. The material for the online sessions and the f2f sessions that will take place in the second or third quarter of 2021 is under development. The structure of the training is clearly defined and presented as an introduction where the participants can see the chapters, the subchapters and the learning path overall.

The categorization of all subchapters of the training using the three criteria resulted in the blended training with 21.65% f2f and 78.35% online sessions as described in Table 1. According to the first criterion, 11.34% of the training would be conveyed in f2f and 96.91% in online sessions. The 11.34% belongs to practical exercises, group projects, discussion sessions, expert discussions that the training subjects contain and need the f2f interaction among participants, trainers and experts as explained above. Based on the second criterion we examined thoroughly the difficulty of the subchapters; increased the f2f session to 19.59% and decreased the online sessions to 80.41%. The third criterion led again to an increase of the f2f sessions to 21.65%. A subchapter, for example, that is thematically close and important for a practical exercise is categorised to the f2f sessions according to the 3rd criterion.

Table 1. Assessment Criteria

Criteria	Training sessions	
	f2f	online
1 st	11.34%	88.66%
2 nd	19.59%	80.41%
3 rd	21.65%	78.35%
Final	21.65%	78.35%

Selected for the delivery and support of this training is the Moodle platform. The participants access the Moodle platform of THI with a personal email address before the f2f session. This platform is user-friendly, fulfils our requirements for data protection and confidentiality and supports the learning process with various features and plugins. While developing the online material, we intend to use all aforementioned types of online videos in order to explore how learning styles are satisfied. The videos are being developed with the green screen technique to add slides and backgrounds, voice-over text and with different camera perspectives, in cases where the content can be promoted. The participants will be able to choose among the different video types and communication channels according to their preferences. After the training, the participants fulfil the Q2 to evaluate the training overall; the content, the learning styles and methods. In telephone or in-person interviews three months after the f2f session the participants will analyse their learning preferences and needs regarding customization. An assessment of learning within this training by taking the exam is not intended because of confidentiality of personal data.

5 CONCLUSION

Through this blended format, THI converted the classroom-based training while surpassing the previous limitations of classroom-based training for corporate training. The methodology of the conversion sought to document and enrich the literature of training development. The blended format we defined in this paper includes various teaching methods and customized content while still offering f2f interaction. This format offers the benefits of an online course that does not interrupt the participants' workflow. It answers the companies' demands while not restraining the different individual learning needs. The new software engineers and architects of different companies, while coming from a wide variety of academic and professional backgrounds acquire a customized outcome based on their personal needs. The importance and benefits of f2f interaction and contact with experts, trainers and employees from other companies and departments enhance the onboarding and networking among the employees and the companies. The example of this training's conversion can also be applied by training developers and educators in other fields. An additional expected research result is the data about the attitude and the preferences of the employees today. Interesting remains to perceive if and how the attitude and the preferences of the employees changed, more than one year after the start of this digital and remote working reality that everyone was forced to enter. Alternatives such as a fully online training are being considered due to the current situation, but the blended format remains a priority for the ongoing project.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) through the project IDEA.

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